

Power Efficient Adiabatic Switching Circuits

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with design opportunities of CMOS based reversible logic circuits employing adiabatic switching methods. The power dissipation an important characteristics are tested by means of SPICE circuit simulation techniques for a CMOS transmission gate based reversible logic circuits, such as Controlled Not gates & Controlled Controlled Not gate. Results from both conventional and adiabatic logic switching simulations are compared. The breakdown of adiabatic operation for these reversible circuits, due to the finite threshold voltages, is tested by checking the logic circuit node current/voltage transient waveform during the logic switching transitions. On the basis of simulation results conclusion has been derived that the performance of reversible logic circuits employing adiabatic switching is better than conventional switching in terms of a factor-power dissipation.

Keywords: Transmission Gate, Adiabatic, Reversible circuits, Pass Gates, Power dissipation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The technological evolution has increased the number of transistors for a given chip area significantly and increased the switching cycle from MHz to GHz range. This inversely proportional reduction in size and boost in performance consequently demands shrinking of supply voltage and effective power dissipation in chips with millions of transistors. This has triggered substantial amount of research in power reduction techniques into almost every aspect of the chip and particularly the processor cores contained in the chip. There are various processor parameters and features such as supply voltage, clock frequency, cache and pipelining which can be optimized to reduce the power consumption of the processor. Some of these concepts have been already established whereas others are still active research areas.

In addition to the energy problem, the heat also becomes an issue. If the released heat from chips cannot be removed quickly, the whole system performance becomes very instable. It is then inevitable to use special IC packaging and more advanced cooling techniques that support quick heat removal, which will increase product cost remarkably. Therefore, exploring the design methodology for low energy based sub-micron circuits is of very great importance.

The adiabatic is a thermodynamics term that is used to describe a process where there is no exchange of heat with the environment. The design based on adiabatic logic reduces the power dissipation tremendously. Very low power dissipation can be achieved by adiabatic switching technique, but at the expense of circuit complexity. Adiabatic logic provides a

technique to recycle the energy stored in the load capacitors rather than traditionally discharging the load capacitors to the ground and wasting this energy [1].

It should be noted that the fully adiabatic operation of the circuit is an ideal condition which may only be approached asymptotically as the switching process is slowed down. In major cases, the energy dissipation associated with a charge transfer event combination of an adiabatic component and a non-adiabatic component. Therefore, reducing all the energy loss to ideally zero is not possible, regardless of the switching speed. With the adiabatic switching approach, the circuit energies are conserved rather than dissipated as heat. Adiabatic logic approach can be used to reduce the power dissipation of the digital systems, depending on the application and the system requirements.

Like many other adiabatic logic families, reversible logic is a dual-rail logic family based on a principle pair of cross-coupled inverters that works on a power-clock, rather than a static DC power-supply. The configuration of the evaluation logic is what makes reversible logic an ideal family to implement fully reversible adiabatic logic.

This logic is constructed from nMOS devices attached between the power-clock and the outputs. These nMOS devices take complementary inputs and are constructed to produce a low-resistance path between the power-clock and the asserted output. The non-asserted output should be left with a high-impedance path to power-clock, and will be pulled low by the cross-coupled n-type devices [2]. This means that the function is evaluated when there is sufficient differential between the

two outputs, but far more importantly means that by using reverse-flowing data, the outputs can be more completely recovered. This should allow losses to be reduced to leakage.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes about reversible adiabatic logic and Section 3 describes the design methodology used to simulate the problem statement. In Section 4 we present the simulation results and discussion about them, finally Section 5 ends with conclusion.

II. REVERSIBLE ADIABATIC LOGIC

The design of logic functions for all dual-rail adiabatic logic families can be achieved by using the same procedures that may be used for Differential Cascode Voltage Switch Logic (DCVSL). These methods are either an Ordered Binary Decision Diagrams (OBDD) or one based upon Quine-McClusky style or extensions of these.

Reversible logic gates logic gates form universal primitives, from which any other logic gate or circuit can be constructed. This paper, examines through simulation techniques, the energy dissipation characteristics for a set of logically and physically reversible logic gates. All the reversible logic circuits presented here have an implementation based upon CMOS transmission gate switches [3]. The fundamental gates, Controlled Not (CN) and Controlled Controlled Not (CCN) are investigated in this paper [4]. These will then be used in future to create the more complex logically and physically reversible circuits of the half, full and ripple carry adder.

Information loss contributes to the overall dissipation of computer circuitry. However its contribution is far outweighed by that generated by other forms of switching dissipation. When the input conditions on a logic gate change state, with the conventional CMOS paradigm [5], power dissipation occurs due to the need to charge or discharge the capacitances associated with the circuit nodes. The power dissipation is given by relation:

$$P_d = f_s C(V_{DD})^2 \quad (1)$$

where f_s is the switching frequency, C is the capacitive load and V_{DD} is the supply voltage. For a gate capacitance of 30fF at a potential of 1V the charging energy is the order of 106 greater than the energy in erasing 1 bit of information [6, 7].

In the adiabatic logic switching paradigm the signal is applied as a ramp rather than as a step function. The energy dissipation for adiabatic switching [8] in a charging or discharging cycle is given by relation:

$$E = \frac{RC}{T} CV_{DD}^2 \quad (2)$$

where T is the rise or fall time respectively.

The adiabatic energy loss is inversely proportional to the rise and fall times of the switching signal, that is the slower the rise and/or fall times the lower the energy dissipation [8, 9]. In order to achieve low power dissipation a penalty of a slower gate switching time accompanies when working with adiabatic computing.

For logic to be reversible, information must not be erased. This means that common functions like “AND” and “OR” cannot be directly implemented because with multiple inputs being reduced to a single output, there is clearly a loss of information. The common logic function with the most potential for reversibility is “XOR”, although “XNOR” would be equally good. The relationship shown in equation 3 means that by preserving input A (or input B) as well as the result of A XOR B, a fully reversible system of gates can be created. This is known as the Feynman Gate and also as a Controlled-NOT (CN) gate [10, 11].

$$P = A, Q = A \oplus B; A = P, B = P \oplus Q; \quad (3)$$

As the Feynman Gate is not a universal gate hence it cannot be used to create every possible logic function. However, the Toffoli Gate [6], which is its three-input variant, and is also known as the Controlled- Controlled-NOT (CCN), is a universal gate that can be used to implement any reversible function. The relationship shown in equation 4 details the operation of a Toffoli Gate.

$$\begin{aligned} P = A, Q = B, R = (A \cdot B) \oplus C; \\ A = P, B = Q, C = (P \cdot Q) \oplus R; \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

III. DESIGN METHODOLOGY

A Controlled Not implemented using reversible logic is shown in Figure 1. The A and $_A$ inputs are the control inputs and are fed directly to the $_P$ and $_P$ outputs and to the control inputs of the transmission gates. The B and $_B$ inputs are the controlled inputs which are routed to the Q and $_Q$ outputs by the transmission gates.

Figure 1: A Controlled Not gate implementation using 4 transmission gates.

During the preceding phase of the power-clock, one of the complementary inputs, “A_L” or “A_H” is asserted. The power-clock VPC is then ramped up, causing the function to evaluate, and be presented on outputs “Q_L” and “Q_H”. The recovery path is then evaluated on “P_L” and “P_H”, and complete recovery can occur through these devices as the power-clock is ramped back down.

It can be seen that without the recovery path denoted by “P_L” and “P_H”, the recovery would only be possible down to the threshold voltage of the back to back connected pMOS devices.

This is because when the outputs of the current stage go into recovery; the drive onto the forward inputs will have already been recovered, resulting in both paths being in a high-impedance state. Figure 2 shows a schematic circuit for a CN gate implemented using four transmission gates. Figure 3 shows the schematic of CCN gate with the help of 8

Figure 2: A Controlled Not gate implementation using 4 TGs.

Figure 3: Controlled Controlled Not gate implementation using 8 TGs.

transmission gates. The A, \bar{A} , B and \bar{B} inputs are the control inputs and are fed directly to the P, \bar{P} , Q and \bar{Q} outputs and to the control inputs of the transmission gates. The C and \bar{C} inputs are the controlled inputs which are routed to the selected R and \bar{R} outputs by the transmission gates. The implementation is based on dual rail logic using -2.5 volts to represent a logic 0 and +2.5 volts to represent a logic1. With this arrangement, there are four inputs and four outputs,

resulting in a true and complementary pair for each input and output signal. The truth table for this CN gate implementation is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Conventional switching i/p voltage waveforms.

The Orcad PSPICE 16.3, was used to create the schematic circuits of the CN and CCN gates. The Orcad PSPICE simulation software by Cadance was used to verify correct logical operation and to capture input signal current and voltage waveform data.

A hierarchical design structure with a transmission gate comprising of an nMOS and a pMOS transistor as the basic building block is used. The ID/VGS characteristics of the nMOS and pMOS transistors for a range of widths were obtained through simulation these were used to select appropriate transistor channel lengths and widths to obtain near ideal logic 0 and logic1 drive strengths[12, 14,18]. Tables 1 and 2 gives the truth table of Controlled Not & Controlled Controlled Not gates respectively.

Table 1: Controlled Not Truth Table

INPUTS				OUTPUTS			
\bar{A}	A	\bar{B}	B	\bar{P}	P	\bar{Q}	Q
1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0

Table 2: Truth table for Controlled Controlled Not Gate

INPUTS						OUTPUTS					
\bar{A}	A	\bar{B}	B	\bar{C}	C	\bar{P}	P	\bar{Q}	Q	\bar{R}	R
1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1
0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1
1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0
1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1
0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0

These control gates are used as library parts, to create the more logically complex half and full adders, which are in turn,

will be used to create the ripple carry adder [19, 20]. Exact logical operation and validation was undertaken using transient response simulation of both logical and physical reversibility.

Energy dissipation for each of the circuits is given by the integration over time, of the voltage current product, for each of the circuit signal inputs. The time interval for integration is over the period of one complete clock cycle [21,23], as defined in equation 5 below

$$E_{Diss} = \sum_{n=1}^N \int_0^T V_n I_n dt \quad (5)$$

where n is a particular input lead from 1 to N, N is the total number of leads, T is the period of one clock cycle, Vn is the voltage waveform on input n and In is the current waveform of input n.

1. Conventional and adiabatic addressing

In this paper the energy dissipation of the CN and CCN reversible logic gates are investigated for two different logic switching methods. The first, conventional logic switching, is a simulation of the energy dissipation performance for a range of different input signal rise and fall times (τ). At the faster speed, this rule becomes equivalent to conventional unrestricted step logic transition. However, as the input logic signal speed are slowed, converting to a ramp function, the adiabatic switching principle, can be evaluated. Figure 4 shows a typical input to a CCN gate where the input signal transitions are in the form of a linear ramp function and where Va, Vb and Vc are the input voltages on the three input signals A, B and C respectively [24].

Figure 4: Conventional switching i/p voltage waveforms.

In this mode, only input signals that have a different final input logic signal change state. Va keeps its voltage of +2.5V representing a constant binary 1 while Vc keeps its voltage of -2.5V representing a constant binary 0. Vb moves from -2.5V to +2.5V as a linear ramp versus time. i.e. changing logic state 0 -> 1.

The adiabatic addressing is yet another switching method that is also used while investigating the performance for energy dissipation of the Controlled Not and Controlled Controlled Not gates. A set of i/p logic switching waveforms for a and Controlled Controlled Not gate when using adiabatic addressing are shown in Table 2 where Va, Vb and Vc are the input voltages associated with the three inputs A, B and C respectively shown in Figure 4. The input logic switching

transition sequence consists of two phases. In the first phase, all input signals move to the midpoint voltage of 0 volts with a controlled rise/fall (τ) time (see Va, Vb, Vc, trise = tfall = T/2, for $t < t_{midpoint}$). In the second phase, input signals move either to their new logic state or back to their original logic state (see Va, Vb, Vc, trise = tfall = T/2, for $t > t_{midpoint}$). Vb moves from -2.5 to +2.5 i.e. changing logic state 0 -> 1. Va moves from +2.5 to 0 and back to +2.5 i.e. maintaining logic state 1. Vc moves from -2.5 to 0 and back to -2.5 i.e. maintaining logic state 0

Figure 5: i/p voltage waveforms for adiabatic switching [8]

IV. RESULTS

The simulation results thus obtained by the above mentioned circuits are graphically shown for energy dissipation against switching time over the range 1ps to 4 μ s.

A. Controlled Not (CN) Gate

The energy dissipation vs rise/fall time response for the conventional logic switching and for the adiabatic logic switching were obtained for two cases:

Case 1: A = 0 & B = 0->1->0 as shown in Figure 6.

Case 2: A = 0->1->0 & B = 0 as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6: Energy dissipation versus switching time for conventional and Adiabatic logic switching of Controlled Not gate for case 1

Figure 7: Energy dissipation *versus* switching time for conventional and adiabatic logic switching of Controlled Not gate for case 2

A. Controlled Controlled Not (CCN) Gate

The energy dissipation *vs* rise/fall time response for the conventional logic switching and for the adiabatic logic switching were obtained for three different cases

Case 3: A = 1; B = 0 & C = 0->1->0 as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Energy dissipation *vs* switching time for conventional and adiabatic logic switching of Controlled Controlled Not gate for case 3

Case 4: C = 1; B = 1 & A = 0->1->0 as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Energy dissipation *vs* switching time for conventional and adiabatic logic switching of Controlled Controlled Not gate for case 4

Case 5: C = 1; B = 0 & A = 0->1->0 as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Energy dissipation *vs* switching time for conventional and adiabatic logic switching of Controlled Controlled Not gate for case 5

It was observed from Figures 8, 9 & 10 that the reversible adiabatic gives better results in terms of power dissipation in comparison to conventional switching logic.

V. CONCLUSION

By the use of circuit simulation techniques the performance of a range of reversible circuit elements operated in conventional and adiabatic logic switching has been evaluated.

The Controlled Not gate and Controlled Controlled Not gate were investigated and comparisons of energy dissipation for conventional and reversible adiabatic logic were done for different values of switching time. It was found that the reversible adiabatic logic circuits show significant reduction of energy dissipation.

In order to reduce energy dissipation the logic switching must be gradual rather than instantaneous. With the circuits examined in this paper, there is a lower limit to the energy dissipation beyond which no significant improvements can be achieved for increasing rise/fall times. This limitation is mainly due to the finite threshold voltage of the MOS transistors and possibly to a lesser extent, the non linear characteristics of the MOS channel resistance.

Our simulations demonstrate that adiabatic addressing when applied to transmission gate logic provides a method of decreasing the energy dissipation when compared with conventional logic switching under certain circumstances.

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